

Development of Subjective Well-being Instrument for Parents Who Have Children with Postlingual Deafness

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: June 18, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Subjective well-being, postlingual deafness children, parents with postlingual deafness children</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3903540</p>	<p><i>Subjective well-being has been widely studied, as well as efforts to develop relevant indicators to reveal well-being, but in expressing subjective well-being to parents who have children with special needs is still limited. On the other hand, an instrument to determine the well-being of parents who have children with special needs is needed along with some research which states that the well-being of a child can be determined, one of which is from a well-being parent in his life. This study aims to develop a subjective well-being measurement instrument for parents who have children with postlingual deafness. The scale developed was based on a review of well-being research conducted by Diener. This study aims to develop a valid subjective well-being measurement instrument for parents who have postlingual deafness children. The instrument preparation step begins with preparing a blueprint, conducting content validation, empirical testing, different power testing, and confirmatory factor analysis test. Respondents involved in this study were 336 parents who have postlingual deafness children domiciled in West Java. The results of the analysis of subjective well-being instruments in parents who have postlingual deafness children show that 30 items compiled have satisfactory psychometric properties when judging from the validity of the content, the different power of the item and the factor structure.</i></p>

Introduction

The study of happiness is an increasingly popular discussion along with the development of positive psychology studies (Seligman, 2002). Nearly all over the world, people consider happiness important. The purpose of human life is to pursue happiness and pleasure (Baumgardner & Crothers, 2010). In psychological studies, this is reflected in studies of subjective well-being (Diener & Ryan, 2009). However, subjective well-being is not defined as hedonism, which is as narrow as the pursuit of temporary physical pleasure (Baumgardner & Crothers, 2010).

Although the study of happiness has been going on for a long time, the concept of happiness itself is still difficult to understand. The term happiness that is often used in the everyday language of conversation has a meaning that is still vague and can be ambiguous. As an alternative, Diener & Ryan (2009) use the term subjective well-being in several scientific studies about happiness. Veenhoven (2012) defines happiness as the degree to which individuals assess their overall quality of life as well. Meanwhile, according to Diener (2000), subjective well-being is interpreted as a person's evaluation of his life, which consists of affective and cognitive evaluation. Specifically, subjective well-being consists of two components, namely the affective component consisting of positive and negative feelings, which means that individuals with high subjective well-being experience life satisfaction, higher positive feelings, and fewer negative emotions; cognitive component is an assessment of one's life satisfaction (Diener & Ryan, 2009). The subjective well-being aspect is the quality of emotions, both in terms of the frequency and intensity experienced by individuals, both pleasant and unpleasant feelings (Kahneman & Deaton, 2010). Positive feelings refer to emotions like satisfaction, whereas negative feelings are more like anger, sadness, and guilt (Baumgardner & Crothers, 2010; Diener et al., 1999; Kahneman & Deaton, 2010). Life satisfaction is what people think about their lives (Kahneman & Deaton, 2010), which does not lead to a specific domain. Nevertheless, feelings and satisfaction of certain domains are generally

measured through an integrated assessment of one's life (Diener & Ryan, 2009). High subjective well-being plays an important role in health and longevity (Diener & Chan, 2011). In the family context, the subjective well-being of a parent can affect a child's well-being. In other words, parents with low subjective well-being, especially those caused by stress, will also affect the welfare of their children (Lee et al., 2016). It also determines life satisfaction in children (Powdthavee & Vignolas, 2007).

There are many reasons why this subjective well-being is important to study. From previous research studies, people who have high subjective well-being relatively have a longer and healthier age (Diener & Chan, 2011), have more role in the community, are less divorced, and are preferred by others (Diener, Oishi, & Tay, 2018). Some countries have even used psychological aspects, such as happiness as an indicator of national success (Oishi, Graham, Kesebir, & Galinha, 2013). Considering the urgency of subjective well-being in human life, the study of constructs and instruments to measure it also becomes important to be studied more deeply.

A construct is worth investigating if it already has a clear conceptual definition and measurement strategy. Through a series of publications, Diener and colleagues propose subjective well-being is a multidimensional construct that has three separate components, namely: 1) positive affection, 2) low negative affection, and 3) cognitive evaluation of life satisfaction (Diener, 2000). Positive and negative affections are included in the domain of affection, while life satisfaction is included in the domain of cognition. However, in some studies, not all researchers use the three-factor model as proposed by Diener.

Some researchers use a two-factor model consisting of affective and cognitive factors, while other researchers treat subjective well-being as a unidimensional model that only looks at subjective well-being one factor as a whole (Arthaud-day, Rode, Mooney, & Near, 2005). The difference in the subjective well-being measurement model has consequences for item analysis and interpretation of the construct. Unidimensional measurement only requires a simple interpretation, because all items on the scale represent one attribute. In contrast, multi-dimensional measurements require more complex interpretations (Widhiarso & Ravand, 2014).

Current views state that affection and cognition are two interrelated and inseparable things. Storbeck & Clore (2007) in his critical study strongly opposed the argument that considers that emotions and cognition are two separate things. Affection plays a full role in the process of cognition where one of the functions of affection is to regulate cognitive processes. A more sophisticated study with neurological measurements also found that emotions and cognition are an interrelated part (Tyng, Amin, Saad, & Malik, 2017). One researcher who treats subjective well-being as a unidimensional construct is Librán (2006).

Another debate about how many factors are appropriate for measuring subjective well-being is related to differences in views about positive and negative affect. Some researchers agree that positive and negative affection are two separate things that are not merely bipolar constructs. When positive affection is dominant, it does not mean negative affection becomes weak. Subsequent studies support many of these findings and underline the importance of assessing positive and negative affections separately (Watson, Clark, & Tellegen, 1988). However, other researchers report positive and negative affect as a contradictory construct and are non-dimensional. For example, Green, Goldman, and Salovey (1993) found a very high correlation between positive and negative affection ($r = -0.85$ to $r = -0.92$).

In addition to the problem of the number of factors in the construct of subjective well-being, another problem related to the measurement of subjective well-being in Indonesia is the lack of information on the scale psychometric property used on parents who have children with special needs. Both the subjective well-being effective instrument is the Positive and Negative Experience Scale (SPANE), developed by Diener et. al (2009) to measure the affective domain of subjective well-being and Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) (Diener, Emmons, Larsen, & Griffin, 1985) to measure the cognitive domain of subjective well-being, measuring general subjective well-being. Meanwhile, the measurement of subjective well-being specifically designed for parents who have children with special needs in this case children who have children with postlingual deafness has not been obtained.

Therefore, another outcome of this research is the presence of psychometric subjective well-being property information specifically for parents who have postlingual deafness children.

The preparation (construction) of measurement instruments is the process of quantifying an attribute (Azwar, 2014). A good instrument must be able to measure what is to be measured (has a high measurement validity) and be able to distinguish subjects that have the attributes measured and those that do not have the attributes measured. It requires a series of implementation procedures in the preparation of the instrument. Azwar (2010) states that the preparation of a measurement instrument must be preceded by the clarity of the attributes to be measured. In the context of this study, the attribute to be measured is subjective well-being parents who have postlingual deafness children. The preparation of instruments requires clear definitions and operationalization of aspects of measuring attributes into behavioral indicators. In this research, the instrument used to compile is an understanding of the understanding and aspects of subjective well-being constructed by Diener (2009). Azwar (2014) explained that the procedure for developing the next measurement instrument was to pour the results of the operationalization of the measurement attributes and behavioral indicators along with the statement items into a certain format called the instrument's blueprint.

The next stage is to test the validity of the contents of the instrument which is intended to determine the effectiveness of the item in distinguishing individuals. In this stage, it requires expert judgment according to the field of the study measured and the measurement expert. The next step is testing the instrument on respondents. In this study, researchers sought to develop subjective well-being measurement instruments for parents who have postlingual deafness children by applying psychometric principles.

The question is: how are the blueprint instruments built? How are the abilities of items arranged to measure the attributes to be measured? What is the ability of each item to distinguish individuals who have measured attributes and individuals who do not have measured attributes?

Method

To answer this question, psychometric methods are used which are procedures for preparing instruments for measuring psychological attributes that are valid using statistics.

Participant. Participants in this study were 336 parents (168 fathers and 168 mothers) who had postlingual deafness children, were biological fathers and mothers of postlingual deafness children, lived with their partners and children who experienced postlingual deafness, were able to communicate verbally and in writing using Indonesian good, domiciled in West Java.

Procedure. The instrument preparation procedure consists of 5 steps. The steps taken include:

Step 1. Arrange the instrument blueprint, the subjective well-being instrument blueprint for parents who have postlingual deafness children illustrates aspects of subjective well-being for parents who have child postlingual deafness, indicators, and items. Items are arranged in the form of behavioral scales. The scale moves from 1-5 which shows how much agreement parents who have postlingual deafness children do in the things indicated in each item. Number 1 (disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (quite agree), 4 (agree), and 5 (strongly agree).

Step 2. Validate the contents of the instrument to find out if the item was compiled. Validation is carried out through an expert judgment process involving 5 doctoral psychologists, and psychometrics experts. The results of the assessment by experts were analyzed using the Lawshe formula to find the coefficient of content validity. With 5 evaluators, Lawshe (1975) proposes that each expert judgment be asked to answer questions for each item with three answer choices namely (1) essential, (2) useful but not essential, (3) unnecessary. According to Lawshe, if more than half of the panelists indicated that the items were important, then the item had at least content validity.

Step 3. Conduct an empirical trial of the scale developed in the previous step. The scaling format uses the Likert model. Trials were conducted on participants.

Step 4. Perform statistically different power tests. The aim is to see the ability of each item to distinguish individuals into various levels of qualitative attributes that are measured based on quantitative scores. Testing is done by correlating the distribution of item scores with the distribution of total scores. The technique used is the Pearson product-moment. An item is said to have a good

difference if the correlation coefficient (rix) 30 0.30 (Azwar, 2014). To facilitate the process of calculating item different power tests used SPSS 20 series.

Step 5. Perform the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) test with the Lisrel 8.80 software on the one-factor model and then look at the resulting chi-square value. If the resulting chi-square (χ^2) value is <0.05 (not significant), then it can be stated that the model is not fit and does not measure one factor. Whereas if the resulting chi-square value is > 0.05 (significant) it can be stated that the model is fit and measures only one factor. If a fit model has been obtained, the next step is to look at the factor load items on the model. The item must have a significant t-value (> 1.96), which means that the item measures what it wants to measure according to the measurement model. Items that are not significant (t-value <1.96) will be eliminated. Next is to look at the value of the existing coefficient load. If the coefficient value on the item is positive, then the item will not be eliminated, and vice versa if the coefficient value on the item is negative then the item will be eliminated. And the last is if there are items that have correlations more than four times, then the item will also be eliminated because it is assumed that the item is not unidimensional by the existing measurement model.

Step 6. Perform final compilation. This is done by comparing the coefficient of the validity of the contents of the Lawshe with the different power coefficients of the item and the results of the confirmatory factor analysis.

Results and Discussion

Blueprint of the instrument. The subjective well-being measuring instrument for parents who have postlingual deafness children in this study consists of 30 items arranged in 5 aspects namely standard of living, physical and mental health, social connectedness, achievement in life, and spiritual. The standard of living aspect consists of 2 indicators, physical and mental health 2 indicators, social connectedness 3 indicators, achievement in life 2 indicators and 1 spiritual indicator. Each indicator is made of items.

Content validity coefficient. This validity shows the ability of the items to measure the attributes to be measured. The content validity test is done through the calculation of the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) and Content Validity Index (CVI) of Lawshe (1975). Before the calculation of CVR and CVI, the researchers conducted an assessment process by panelists (expert judgment) consisting of 5 panelists who were experts in the fields of psychology and psychometry. According to Lawshe (1975) the value of the CVR of each item can be calculated with $[(n_e - N / 2)] / N / 2$, where n_e is the number of panelists stating an item is 'agreed', and N is the number of panelists. Then later from the results of this calculation the CVR value that is considered good must pay attention to the CVR value table based on the number of panelists. Panelists in this study amounted to 5 people, then from the Lawshe table (1975), the minimum value of CVR for each item is 0.99. The CVR calculation value for each item can be seen in Table 1.1 below.

Table 1

Calculation of CVR Subjective Well-Being Items

Aspect	No Item	CVR
standard of living	1	1
	2	1
	3	1
physical and mental health	4	1
	5	1
	6	1
	7	1
	8	1
social connectedness	9	1
	10	1
	11	1
	12	1
	13	1
	14	1
	15	1

	16	1
	17	1
	18	1
Achievement in life	19	1
	20	1
	21	1
	22	1
	23	1
	24	1
	25	1
Spiritual	26	1
	27	1
	28	1
	29	1
	30	1

The coefficient of power is different. The ability of the item to distinguish individuals who have the attributes measured and those that do not have the attributes measured or distinguish individuals into various levels of qualitative attributes that are measured based on quantitative scores, is shown by the magnitude of the coefficient. An item is said to have a good / high difference if the correlation between the item's score and the total scale score is equal to or more than 0.30 ($r_{ix} \geq 0.30$). If ($r_{ix} \geq 0.25$) can still be considered (moderate / sufficient power difference), but if $r_{ix} \leq 0.20$ then the item has a low power difference (Azwar, 2014). The analysis showed that of the 30 items tested empirically to parents who have postlingual deafness children, these 30 items had ($r_{ix} \geq 0.30$).

Table 2
Calculation of different power coefficients

No. Item	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Sig.
1	.444	Significant
2	.481	Significant
3	.345	Significant
4	.636	Significant
5	.362	Significant
6	.346	Significant
7	.352	Significant
8	.447	Significant
9	.472	Significant
10	.481	Significant
11	.386	Significant
12	.513	Significant
13	.484	Significant
14	.567	Significant
15	.478	Significant
16	.538	Significant
17	.537	Significant
18	.421	Significant

19	.422	Significant
20	.494	Significant
21	.535	Significant
22	.608	Significant
23	.408	Significant
24	.556	Significant
25	.574	Significant
26	.550	Significant
27	.472	Significant
28	.536	Significant
29	.623	Significant
30	.519	Significant

The coefficient of construct validity. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) test with Lisrel 8.80 software was carried out to test the construct validity of this instrument. First, an analysis of each aspect of subjective well being was carried out. After obtaining the results of the analysis with the conditions of all significant items for each aspect, then the factor score estimation is performed as data for the next stage of analysis. Second, the factor score data for each aspect is used as data to test whether the five aspects, namely the standard of living, physical and mental health, social connectedness, achievement in life and spiritual significance to measure subjective well being in parents who have postlingual deafness children. In assessing the criteria of model fit, according to Schumacker & Lomax (2004) recommend Chi-square (χ^2), df and p-level > 0.05 (not significant is good); NFI, GFI, CFI (good if > 0.95); and RMSEA with confidence intervals (good if < .05).

Table 3

Test suitability of the model aspect of subjective well-being

No	Aspek	X^2	df	p	RMSEA	NFI	GFI	CFI
1	standard of living	0.00	0	1	0.000	1	1	1
2	physical and mental health	1.93	3	0.586	0.000	1	1	1
3	social connectedness	60.78	39	0.054	0.041	0.98	0.99	0.97
4	Achievement in life	17.60	6	0.347	0.017	0.98	1	0.99
5	Spiritual	0.00	0	1	0.000	1	1	1

Concerning the Chi-square value (χ^2), df, the level of p-value; NFI, GFI, CFI; and RMSEA (Schumacker & Lomax, 2004) can be concluded that the measurement model is compatible with the data. Based on these results, it can be continued at the next stage, which is to see whether the significant item measures the factors to be measured. Testing is done by looking at the value of t for each factor load coefficient, as in the following table.

Table 4
Test the significance of subjective well-being items

Observed	Latent	SLF	SE	t-value	p-value	Sig
1	SL	0.67	0.67	12.83	1.00	S
2	SL	0.64	0.89	12.03	1.00	S
3	SL	0.51	1.22	9.45	1.00	S
4.	KF	0.50	1.05	9.07	0.58	S
5.	KF	0.58	0.89	11.03	0.58	S
6.	KF	0.59	0.91	11.31	0.58	S
7.	KF	0.61	0.92	11.70	0.58	S
8.	KF	0.61	0.99	11.63	0.58	S
9.	SC	0.65	0.81	12.93	0.06	S
10.	SC	0.70	0.82	14.43	0.06	S
11.	SC	0.61	0.91	11.98	0.06	S
12.	SC	0.68	0.81	13.67	0.06	S
13.	SC	0.65	0.84	13.03	0.06	S
14.	SC	0.61	1.00	11.88	0.06	S
15.	SC	0.65	0.88	13.12	0.06	S
16.	SC	0.55	0.96	10.52	0.06	S
17.	SC	0.64	0.83	12.71	0.06	S
18.	SC	0.61	0.99	12.03	0.06	S
19.	SC	0.59	0.96	11.43	0.06	S
20.	AL	0.59	0.92	10.92	0.35	S
21.	AL	0.55	0.95	10.10	0.35	S
22.	AL	0.59	1.14	10.98	0.35	S
23.	AL	0.50	1.51	8.89	0.35	S
24.	AL	0.53	1.09	9.76	0.35	S
25.	AL	0.50	1.15	7.77	0.35	S
26.	AL	0.50	0.99	8.80	0.35	S
27.	AL	0.50	1.32	8.34	0.35	S
28.	SP	0.57	1.10	9.89	1.00	S
29.	SP	0.63	0.79	11.13	1.00	S
30.	SP	0.73	0.69	12.97	1.00	S

Based on the calculation results of the significant items in the table above. It is known that all items in subjective well-being instruments in parents who have significant postlingual deafness children so that it is said that all items in subjective well-being instruments in parents who have postlingual deafness children are valid.

Then explained in the section below about the path diagram of the CFA calculation results for each dimension with items in the dimension of subjective well-being in parents who have postlingual deafness children.

Standard of living

Physical and mental health

Chi-Square=0.00, df=0, P-value=1.00000, RMSEA=0.000

Chi-Square=1.93, df=3, P-value=0.58610, RMSEA=0.000

Social Connectedness

Chi-Square=60.78, df=39, P-value=0.05434, RMSEA=0.041

Achievement in Life

Chi-Square=17.60, df=16, P-value=0.34761, RMSEA=0.017

Spiritual

Chi-Square=0.00, df=0, P-value=1.00000, RMSEA=0.000

Based on the standardized path diagram for the five aspects of subjective well-being shows the number of standardized loading factors (SLF) owned per item questionnaire. This number has been tested to have a good number or can be said to be valid because the SLF number owned is ≥ 0.5 .

Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion in this study it can be concluded that all items in the subjective well-being instrument in parents who have postlingual deafness children are significant so it is said that all items in this subjective well-being instrument are valid. The subjective well-being scale for parents who have post-sexual deafness children is the first step to obtain instruments that are appropriate to the context of parents who have children with special needs.

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